

Mucosal health reveals the potential of peracetic acid as a routine disinfectant in atlantic salmon parr in recirculating aquaculture system

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Peracetic acid (PAA) is regarded as a promising disinfectant for improving biosecurity in aquaculture due to its broad spectrum of activity against a number of pathogens, short contact time, low dependency on pH, and rapid degradation into harmless residues. In this study, we documented over a 4-week period the health and welfare effects of periodic (every 3 days) and continuous administration of 1 mg/L PAA in Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) parr reared in a recirculating aquaculture system. The group without PAA served as control. Mucosal organs (i.e. gills, skin, olfactory organ), plasma, and skin mucus were collected at weeks 0, 2 and 4. PAA administration induced changes in the antioxidant balance of the mucosal surfaces as shown by the altered expression of genes encoding for antioxidant defence, where treatment-related changes were more apparent at week 4. The genes such as *glutathione S-transferase*, *glutathione peroxidase*, and *glutathione reductase* were responsive to the treatments, especially in the gills and olfactory organ. However, there was no clear distinction that could be established between the two administration modes. PAA induced structural changes in the mucosal organs and these alterations were prominent in the gills and olfactory organ. Antioxidant capacity of plasma remained unaltered, but an increase was observed in the skin mucus especially in the continuous group. The plasma level of reactive oxygen species was significantly lower in both PAA-treated groups. This study demonstrated that salmon parr mounted physiological adaptive responses to PAA administration. Mucosal responses revealed that the gills and olfactory organ were sensitive to PAA than the skin. The minimal alterations in mucosal health status provide support to the potential application of PAA as a routine disinfection to improve the rearing environment of salmon in RAS.

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